

Research Article

Home Environment and Academic Achievement: A Correlational Study of Elementary Level Students of Azad Jammu and Kashmir

Dr. Khatiba Akhter* & Samra Malik

Department of Education, University of Kotli, AJ&K

Article Info.	Abstract
Received: 17-Jan-24 Revised: 05-Mar-24 Accepted: 19-Mar-24 Published: 31-Mar-24	This study was conducted to determine the relationship between home environment and academic achievement of students at elementary level. The current study was quantitative in nature and survey method were used for the data collection. The population of the study were consisted of 2492 students of all Government elementary schools of Kotli AJ&K. The researcher selected 350 students by using simple random sampling technique. Standardized questionnaire developed by Smekh and leuin (1990) were used for the collection of data. The researcher personally visited the government schools of Kotli AJ&K the for collection of data. The researcher applied frequency, percentage, mean and Pearson's correlation for the analysis of data. It is concluded that parental communication is basic aspect of home environment and is essential in academic achievement of students. It is recommended that schools should actively promote and facilitate effective communication channels between parents, teachers and students.
Keywords:	Home environment, Role of father, Role of mother, Role of child, Role of family, Academic achievement
Corresponding Author:	Dr. Khatiba Akhter
Email:	khatiba.akhter@yahoo.com
How to Cite:	Akhter, A. & Malik, S. (2024). Home Environment and Academic Achievement: A Correlational Study of Elementary Level Students of Azad Jammu and Kashmir. <i>International Journal of Emerging Trends in Education</i> , 2(1), 1-16.

Introduction

The family, or home, is the first institution a kid attends; in other words, it is the setting where early education and socialization take place. The home is the main and most significant human institution for a child's socialization. The home environment has a significant impact on the child's behavior as it gives him or her the elements needed for healthy physical, cognitive, psychosocial and behavioral development (Newman, Gozu, Guan, Lee, Li, & Sasaki, 2015). The home environment consists of a variety of moral and ethical principles as well as an intellectual, social, and emotional atmosphere created by family members to support a person's healthy growth. Therefore, a home may satisfy every human need. A child's development takes place largely at home. Students' home environments may either strengthen or weaken their personalities (Sharma, 2011).

The two primary areas of the human environment that are seen to be extremely important in an educational setting are the home and the school. Both the home and the school are significant environmental factors that have a significant impact on adolescents' behavior and academic achievement. Thus, understanding the entire process of the school and home climate and how it affects students' behavior and academic progress is crucial (Kutsyuruba, Klinger & Hussain, 2015). It has been demonstrated that a number of elements in the home are significant, including the mother's attentiveness, her engagement and style of discipline, the environment's structure, the availability of suitable learning resources, and the opportunity for daily stimulation. Children's intellectual development is accelerated by parents who create a play and learning environment that is warm, attentive, and supportive; they also foster curiosity and inquiry (Bick et al., 2019).

One aspect of a student's life that might have an impact on grades is their home environment, which serves as the basis for learning. According to the University of Minnesota Extension, giving students the chance to study outside of the classroom can help them succeed in the classroom. Experts concluded that a young child's academic achievement was most significantly influenced by the mother's educational attainment (Darling-Hammond & Cook-Harvey, 2018).

Any student's academic achievement is inextricably linked to their home environment; a youngster who lives in a good household has emotional stability. One of the main purposes of education is to prepare young people to contribute to society. The informal training process starts at home. The child's home is the first location he or she inhabits after being born (O'Malley, Voight, Renshaw & Eklund, 2015). According to Morin, Demers, Turcotte and Mongeau (2013) a healthy learning environment has an impact on students' ability to attain high marks on standardized examinations. In a similar vein, Pashiardi (2008) discovered that a school environment that is encouraging, kind, pleasant, and loving promotes student happiness and optimal learning. Another study conducted by Nouri (2015) indicated that there is a significant correlation between student success and school size in Pakistan. The results of the same study also indicated a significant correlation between student achievement and class size. Additionally, there is a favorable correlation between student achievement and the school atmosphere. Kaur and Gupta's (2011) research has demonstrated that a child's development is positively impacted by a supportive environment both at home and at school. Majoribanks (1996) asserts that several studies demonstrate the significance of parental participation, family size, and socioeconomic position in influencing adolescents' academic success. Therefore, families with supportive intellectual, social, emotional, and physical traits have a good impact on people's whole development, especially that of children.

The study's primary goal is to investigate the connection between elementary school pupils in Kotli, AJ&K, and their home environments and academic progress. This study is significant because it might yield insightful data on the ways in which factors such as parental engagement, study spaces, and family support impact children's academic performance. Teachers and parents may employ particular tactics and build pleasant home settings by better understanding this link in order to improve the academic accomplishments of pupils in the region.

Objective of the Study

1. To identify the elements of home environment of students at elementary level
2. To examine the academic achievement of students at elementary level
3. To determine the relationship between home environment and academic achievement of students at elementary level

Research Questions

1. What are the elements of home environment of students at elementary level?
2. What are the factors that influence the academic achievement of elementary-level students?
3. Is there any significant relationship between home environment and academic achievement of students at elementary level?

Review of Related Literature

Home Environment

The home environment includes the actions of family members as well as the accessibility of amenities like a phone, internet, and car that can have an impact on a student's personality and secondary school academic performance. The surrounds of a person's home are their home environment. The entirety of all internal and external factors influencing an organism's ability to survive, develop, and thrive is its environment, right? It is an effect that a person encounters subsequent to the genetic process via the plasma gene (Kim, 2011).

The term "home environment" refers to the familial background of the kid and all the material and human resources that are present in the home and have an impact on the child's quality of life, including the parents' occupation, degree of education, and social and economic standing as well as the socializing spaces in the home. As a result, the family serves as the child's primary socialization setting and the basis for their education, both of which are provided by other socialization agents. Due to the urgent need to train the youth, the government has stepped in to support and assist families and educational institutions in carrying out this enormous task by establishing the national education policy, which includes the national education objectives (Sarsour, *et. al.*, 2011).

Financial resources within the family, which are linked to the employment and educational achievement of the parents, frequently suggest more chances for learning to occur at home and in school. Family background is, in fact, the cornerstone of a child's development; hence, the kind, size, socioeconomic level, and educational background of a family all have a significant impact on a child's ability to learn and integrate into society. A child's psychological, emotional, social, and economic well-being are greatly influenced by their family environment contend that because parents are a person's first socializers, their home environment has an impact on them (Ajila & Olutola, 2000).

Teen aspirations are influenced by their home circumstances. A child's socialization starts at home, with their family. A child's identification with society, culture, religion, or socioeconomic status is shaped by their family environment. Thus, a child's life and academic achievement at school are still greatly influenced by their household. It must be acknowledged that the roles that houses play

in various social hierarchies vary. As an illustration, some people are more well-known, wealthy, or have other advantages, but others have greater life experience and understanding of how to function in a social or academic setting (Nichols, Kotchick, McNamara Barry, & Haskins, 2010). More than any other factor, the home environment affects a student's ability to succeed. While discouragement from the environment only serves to lower pupils' skills, encouragement from the environment may stimulate learning and improve one's potential. Academic accomplishment is the acquisition of skills in academic work as judged by examinations administered by teachers. Academic success is a gift that comes from doing assignments in a classroom. Students' learning level was significantly impacted by their home environment. The environment in the home has an impact on a child's capacity to learn both directly and indirectly. Furthermore, family life and the home environment offer a system of intellectual, social, and physical components that directly impact student development (Efriza, Caska & Makhdalena, 2020).

Students' academic success is influenced by a wide range of circumstances. These influences might come from classmates, the family, or the school. Examined learning from several angles and discovered that a student's aptitude, interests, family environment, relationships with peers, and the type of learning materials they are exposed to all had a big impact on their learning. The most important aspect among all the others is the home environment. A child's first educational setting is their mother, who also serves as the child's first teacher (Fanti & Henrich, 2010).

The term "home environment" refers to a variety of moral and ethical standards as well as the intellectual, emotional, and social atmosphere that family members create to support a person's healthy growth. Therefore, a home may satisfy every human need. A child's home is a crucial site for their growth. Students' home environments may either strengthen or weaken their personalities. It also has an impact on pupils' academic performance. An investigation on the same subject, for instance, revealed a strong correlation between academic achievement and the family environment (Sharma, 2011). The findings of Mohanraj's (2005) study demonstrated that, in addition to other variables like home adjustment, family environment had a substantial link with academic success. As a result, there has been a lot of discussion on the home environment, with several topics being covered (Runco & Cayirdag, 2013).

Role of Father in Home Environment

Achievement is directly correlated with family size and economic status. The primary variation is explained by learning activities, family environment, and academic success. Socioeconomic status, particularly the effect of parents' income and the parent-child bond on the academic achievement of Japanese high school students. Presumably, negating the impact of students' home environments will not enable educators and educational institutions to address achievement inequalities (Cetin & Taskin, 2016).

For the stability and overall growth of the family, the role of the father in the house is crucial. Fathers are frequently the pillars of strength and stability in their households. They offer counsel and emotional assistance in addition to financial security. Their presence can provide their spouse and kids a sense of comfort and security, promoting a caring and well-rounded family atmosphere (Wood, Moore, Clarkwest & Killewald, 2014).

Fathers are extremely important to a child's development and education. They provide a different viewpoint and parenting approach that goes well with the mother's. Fathers may teach their children valuable life lessons, morals, and values by modeling these traits for them. Their emotional and cognitive growth is aided by their engagement in their children's life, which helps them mature into responsible, well-rounded adults (Yaffe, 2023).

Fathers frequently take an active role in caring for their families and doing housework, which challenges gender stereotypes and fosters equality. Their participation in household chores like cooking, cleaning, and child care makes the home more peaceful and well-balanced. A father's support, direction, and active involvement in the family life are all important aspects of his varied position in the house and add to the family's general happiness and well-being (Ben-Arieh *et al.*, 2014).

Role of Mother in Home Environment

One aspect of a student's life that might have an impact on grades is their home environment, which serves as the basis for learning. According to the University of Minnesota Extension, giving students the chance to study outside of the classroom can help them succeed in the classroom. Experts concluded that a young child's academic achievement was most significantly influenced by the mother's educational attainment (Harding, Morris & Hughes, 2015).

Learning what it's like to love a child is enough to permanently transform hearts. Loving children makes us feel good, is natural, and cannot be fulfilled by anything else. The secret to a child's emotional stability and maturity as they become adults is to make them feel loved. To create a stable atmosphere for your infant, from cuddles to seeing them develop into their own tiny personalities, childhood, and finally adulthood, the key is to remain steady in your unconditional love. It is more than just feeling what they are feeling and wanting to offer them everything you have. To genuinely love your children is to sacrifice oneself. Being a true parent isn't always easy, but it also doesn't mean putting yourself last all the time. Love is an emotion, after all, but as parents, we must recognize that a child's definition of love frequently falls short of what they truly need. I am not speaking of providing emotional stability; a child need not strive to be "better" in order to receive love (Taylor, 2010).

A mother's diverse position in the home is essential to fostering a happy and healthy family life. First of all, moms frequently act as the family's emotional pillar. Their spouse and children receive love, care, and emotional support from them, which fosters a safe and comfortable environment where family members may flourish. Strong emotional ties within the family are mostly fostered by a mother's capacity to listen, sympathize, and provide advice (Ruthven, Buchanan & Jardine, 2018).

Mothers have a crucial role in the administration and structure of the home. They frequently take on duties including grocery shopping, cooking, cleaning, washing, and making sure everyone in the family is well. The comfort and efficiency of the family are enhanced by their maintenance of the structural and operational elements of the house (Morin, Demers, Turcotte & Mongeau, 2013).

Instilling values, morality, and a feeling of duty in children is typically a major job of mothers. They act as role models, imparting valuable life skills and assisting kids in growing into responsible, kind, and well-adjusted adults. A mother's position in the home is vital because her advice and influence may have a lasting effect on a child's character and development. In general, mothers play a combination of organizing, directing, and nurturing roles in the home, fostering a loving, caring atmosphere where people may develop and thrive (Kim & Esquivel, 2011).

Role of Child in Home Environment

The physical surroundings of children's homes serve as the basis for their educational activities at home. Children's home environments both encourage and constrain them to engage in educational activities there. Since a youngster only spends five to six hours at school and must make the most

of their remaining time at home, practicing for class and preparing for it at home are essential. Making the most of a child's home time entails creating an educational atmosphere, which is crucial for raising children's academic achievement (Hart, 2013).

Children educational activities at home are based on the physical environment of their home. Home facilities of children enable and restrain them in practicing educational activities at home. Class preparation and practice at home are fundamental for child, as a child spends only five and six hours at school and the remaining time is spent at home which needs to be utilized properly. The proper utilization of home time of child means provision of educational environment at home, which plays a dominant role in improving the educational performances of children. The creation of Parent Teacher Councils and Associations in schools is a critical step in encouraging parent participation in their children's education and provides a more thorough explanation of the home environment and how it affects students' academic performance. Children can pick up knowledge from their parents and elders thanks to the power of imitation. Children may learnt a lot from their parents and other family members through activities like watching TV, eating lunch, supper, and breakfast at home (Donnelly & Lambourne, 2011).

Role of Family in Home Environment

In a 1997 study, Halle et al. examined the effects of the family on low-income children's academic achievement. They discovered that mothers with higher levels of education had higher expectations for their kids' academic performance, and that these expectations were linked to the kids' later success in reading and mathematics. They also discovered that these more optimistic attitudes and expectations were associated with greater levels of achievement-related behavior by moms in the house and more optimistic views of accomplishment held by the kids (Yeung, 2002). In a research on the effects of poverty on young children's cognitive and linguistic development as well as their early school accomplishment. Parent education has a significant role in predicting children's success. Money has a significant impact on early children's development, the processes underlying this influence have not received much attention. Family process models (Ibid) have generally looked at how parenting practices, like how the home environment is structured, affect the academic achievements of children (Bicer, Capraro & Capraro, 2013).

Family interactions take place often at home. Family members receive instructions from the head of the household to carry out household chores both within and outside the home. The tone, language, and communication style of the family head reflect his or her attitude, and the family members' responses to the head of the family also reflect the same elements, which together make up the family members' attitude toward the head of the family and his or her communication. Additionally, a significant component involving the in-depth relationships of family members is family decisions. It is the point at which the significance of a family member's statement or viewpoint may be assessed. Students' social development is aided by families that include their kids in decision-making because it gives them the confidence and self-worth they need (Galvin, Braithwaite & Bylund, 2015).

Parents who are frequently characterized as "controlling" or "authoritarian" have generally been shown to predict low academic accomplishment when it comes to the correlations between parenting style and academic performance (Chao, 2001). Research findings indicate that kids raised by authoritarian parents often display withdrawn and fearful attitudes, lack independence, and depend on authoritative people for decision-making, which weakens their sense of personal worth and accountability. Furthermore, children's intrinsic drive might be diminished by the intense parental pressure that comes with the authoritarian approach, making them dependent on

outside sources and impeding their ability to learn. These kinds of actions frequently lead to poor communication skills, which are a crucial indicator of future success. Research has actually shown that placing too much attention on it might actually alienate kids. A child's academic competency and success may suffer if they are overly confident in themselves and have their studies interfered with (Newma *et. al.*, 2015).

More educated parents are more inclined to participate in their children's schooling. More educated parents understand the operation of schools and are probably used to the layout of the classroom. Since educated parents respect education and often encourage their children to value and actively engage in acquiring education, parents' educational background has an impact on kids' motivation and performance. Better economic conditions are indicated by parents with higher occupational levels, which translates into material support for their children's education (Dzever, 2015).

During the course of his research, he discovered that parents of academically accomplished individuals tend to work in professional, administrative, and clerical capacities, whereas parents of underachievers tend to seek careers in trades, production labor, and semi-skilled and unskilled jobs. According to this theory, the majority of underachievers originate from homes with lower socioeconomic status, and the psychological support provided in these settings does nothing to enhance intelligence (Al-Matalka, 2014).

The atmosphere that permeates the house is referred to as the family environment, and it differs from culture to culture, society to society, and family to family. The father, mother, grandparents, sisters, brothers, uncle, aunt, and so on make up the family environment refer to the entirety of the family environment, considering the social conditions that exist inside the family (Duh, Belak & Milfelner, 2010).

Every culture has a distinct definition of family. Family is defined as "A social group consisting of parents and their children" in the Collins Student Dictionary. Members of the family are granted status. When a kid is born, their family bestows upon them a name or a lineage. He or she inherits the attitudes and values of the family, regardless of whether they are born into a high class or lower-class background. Furthermore, the family serves as the child's primary socialization resource. The family instills the next generation with the group's beliefs, way of life, and culture through instruction, indoctrination, and example. Children also pick up the family's expectations, goals, and conduct norms, which shape their personalities. Families vary in their expectations, aspirations, and behaviors (Mollborn, Rigles & Pace, 2021).

Student Academic Achievement

Achievement is the degree of success one has after completing a task. It might take many different forms, including intellectual, personal, and social. Academic achievement is also known as scholastic accomplishment. The level that a student in a certain class has attained is known as academic attainment. It is the degree of mastery attained in professions and crafts. It is stated in terms of marks or grades. The culmination of all the behavioral changes students make as a result of their educational experiences is their academic performance. It is the academic performance of a pupil. It is the ability to act after completing a course of study. In the contemporary educational climate, students' academic success is the top focus (Artino, 2012).

Educational studies and literature have offered several facets of academic success. For instance, the accomplishment of learning objectives as well as other related goals such professional success, skill and competency acquisition, perseverance, and academic performance. The graphic that follows presents these ingrains. A formal start to investigating the factors that influence academic success, as seen by Binet's attempts to forecast kids academic success based on their IQ levels. Intelligence is the most important predictor of academic accomplishment, according to a mountain

of data. There is a direct correlation between accomplishment and intellect, as shown by Thorndike (1963).

Achievement is the level of achievement attained by a person after finishing a task. It could come in several forms such as social, personal, or academic. Scholastic accomplishment is another name for academic achievement. Academic accomplishment is the level that a student in a particular class has reached. It is the level of expertise achieved in crafts and vocations. It is expressed in grades or marks. Academic accomplishment is the sum of all the behavioral adjustments that pupils make as a result of their educational experiences. It is a student's learning performance. After completing a term of study, it is the capacity to perform (Ahmad, *et. al.*, 2021).

The academic success of a student is determined in a number of ways, including exam results, CGPA, and GPA. Globally, students' academic success is gauged using their GPA. Researchers utilize test results or results from the prior year to examine how well students performed in a certain topic or year. Academic performance is demonstrated by specific learning over a certain period of time, as demonstrated by exam scores, instructor grades, and subject-specific percentiles. The capacity of students to pass a test is correlated with their accomplishment. Academic ability in math and social studies has occasionally been measured, and the results have been linked to personality qualities including extraversion, conscientiousness, agreeableness, openness to new experiences, and neuroticism (Al-Naggar *et. al.*, 2015).

Role of Home Environment and Students Academic Achievement

Study conducted in Kitui, Kenya on the impact of home environment on academic performance of secondary school pupils in public schools revealed several types of connections between academic achievement in public schools and home environment. The financial situation of a student's parents affects their academic achievement. This is a result of the parents' ability to supply additional educational resources like books and timely payment of the school's tuition. The pupil will probably do better academically as a result of this. Parents and families may positively impact their children's academic achievement in public secondary schools by participating in school-sponsored events, monitoring their progress, and providing encouragement. This is probably going to have a significant impact on raising the student's performance (Imoleit, 2022).

In public secondary schools, a student's academic success is significantly impacted by their parents' parenting style. As a result, academic success was favorably correlated with authoritative parenting, but high performance was adversely correlated with authoritarian and permissive parenting. In investigating how the home environment affects secondary school children's academic performance, Egunsola (2014) discovered the following correlations between parents' educational background, socioeconomic position, place of residence, and employment (Areepattamanni, 2010).

He really noted that there is a relationship and that they have a big impact on the academic achievement of pupils in Adamawa State secondary schools when it comes to Agricultural Science. These findings are important information that should be noted by all parties involved in educational administration, practice, and evaluation. In particular, parents of students enrolled in home education programs should encourage their children's academic success by creating a home environment that is conducive to improved academic performance (Imoleit, 2022).

More than any other factor, the home environment affects a student's ability to succeed. While discouragement from the environment only serves to lower pupils' skills, encouragement from the environment may stimulate learning and improve one's potential. Academic accomplishment is the acquisition of skills in academic work as judged by examinations administered by teachers. Academic success is a gift that comes from doing assignments in a classroom. Students' learning

level was significantly impacted by their home environment. The environment in the home has an impact on a child's capacity to learn both directly and indirectly. Furthermore, the family-style environment and the house itself offer a system of intellectual, social, and physical characteristics that directly influence student learning (Wang & Sheikh-Khalil, 2014).

Socioeconomic status is related to the supportive nature of families, aspirations, and educational activities conducted at home. The educational environment that is created by families with varying socioeconomic backgrounds has an impact on the academic performance of the kid (Porumbu & Necşoi, 2013).

Research Methodology

The study was quantitative in nature. A descriptive method was used to conduct the research. In descriptive method survey technique was used to collect the data from the students. All the elementary school students of Kotli AJ&K were the population of the study. Sample of the study were comprised of 350 by using sample random sampling technique. Standardized questionnaire were used for collection of data which was developed by Smekh and Lewin in 1990. The total number of statements were 52, the researcher used 15 statements, according to the demands of study. The questionnaire was validated from three educational experts of the field of education. The reliability of instrument was checked by Cronbach's alpha statistical technique. The reliability of the instrument for section one regarding Parental Communication was .732 and the reliability of the instrument for section two regarding Home Learning Environment was .843 and the reliability of the instrument for section three regarding Emotional Support was .764. The researcher personally visited all the Govt. Schools of Elementary Level in Kotli AJ&K and collected the data by distributed 350 questionnaire to the students. The researcher analyzed the data through statistical package for social science software (SPSS) version 22 by using mean score, frequency and percentage and Pearson correlation.

Results

Table 1

Mean Analysis of Parental communication

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	My parents set clear targets for me.	350	4.12
2.	My parents take interest in my academic progress.	350	4.46
3.	My parents emphasize on my higher education.	350	4.41
4.	My parents interact with my teachers.	350	2.78
5.	My parents discuss about progress of my studies with me.	350	4.23

Table 1 indicates the descriptive analysis of parental communication. The table further showed that the majority of students reported that their parents set clear targets for them (mean = 4.12), take interest in their academic progress (mean = 4.46), and emphasize the importance of higher education (mean = 4.41). However, there appears to be a lower level of parental interaction with teachers, as indicated by a lower mean score of 2.78. Nonetheless, students reported that their parents frequently discuss their academic progress with them (mean = 4.23).

Table 2

Mean Analysis of Home learning environment

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	Learning material is provided to me at my home.	350	4.47
2.	Tutor is arranged for me at home.	350	2.81
3.	I am allowed to watch television for a specific time.	350	3.97
4.	My family members make study schedule for me.	350	4.23
5.	In case of my mistakes, my privileges are withdrawn.	350	4.10

Table 2 illustrates the students' perceptions of their home learning environment. The table indicated that learning materials are readily available to them at home (mean = 4.47), and their family members actively engage in supporting their education by making study schedules (mean = 4.23) and withdrawing privileges in response to mistakes (mean = 4.10). However, there appears to be a lower level of provision for tutoring at home, as indicated by a lower mean score of 2.81. Additionally, students reported being allowed to watch television for a specific time as part of their home learning environment (mean = 3.97).

Table 3

Mean Analysis of Appreciation for my qualities

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	My family members appreciate my qualities.	350	3.93
2.	My family members share my success stories with others.	350	3.68
3.	My family members amend me politely.	350	2.74
4.	My family members remind me my previous failures.	350	3.88
5.	My parents attend school programs.	350	4.06

Table 3 presents data on students' perceptions of appreciation for their qualities within their family environment. The table illustrated that feeling appreciated by their family members for their qualities (mean = 3.93) and noted that their parents attend school programs, indicating support and involvement in their academic endeavors (mean = 4.06). However, there appears to be room for improvement in terms of how failures are addressed within the family environment, as students reported relatively high mean scores for family members reminding them of previous failures (mean = 3.88). Additionally, the mean score for family members amending students politely was lower (mean = 2.74), suggesting a potential area for enhancing communication and support within the family context.

Table 4

Correlation: Parental communication and Academic Achievement

	Mean	SD	R	P
Parental communication	20.06	3.144	0.638	0.000
Academic achievement	73.71	7.007		

Table 4 shows the results of Pearson’s Correlation used to find out correlation between Parental Communication and Academic Achievement. The result indicated that there was a significant relationship between Parental Communication (M=20.02, SD=3.144) and Academic Achievement (M=73.71, SD=7.007) of students. Table 4.16 further indicated there was a moderate and positive relationship between Parental Communication and Academic Achievement as $r=0.638$.

Table 5

Correlation: Home learning environment and Academic Achievement

	Mean	SD	r	P
Home environment	19.60	3.633	0.647	0.000
Academic achievement	73.71	7.007		

Table 5 shows the results of Pearson’s Correlation used to find out correlation between Home Learning Environment and Academic Achievement. The result indicated that there was a significant relationship between Home Learning Environment (M=19.60, SD=3.633) and Academic Achievement (M=73.71, SD=7.007) of students. Table 4.11 further indicated there was a moderate and positive relationship between Home Learning Environment and Academic Achievement as $r=0.647$.

Table 6

Correlation: Emotional support and Academic Achievement

	Mean	SD	r	P
Emotional support	17.34	3.329	0.462	0.000
Academic achievement	73.71	7.007		

Table 6 shows that results of Pearson’s Correlation used to find out correlation between Emotional Support and Academic Achievement. The result indicated that there was a significant relationship between Emotional Support (M=17.34, SD=3.329) and Academic Achievement (M=73.71, SD=7.007) of students. Table 4.18 further indicated there was a moderate and positive relationship between Emotional Support and Academic Achievement as $r=0.462$.

Table 7

Correlation: Home Environment and Academic Achievement of Students

	Mean	SD	r	P
Home Environment	57.00	8.360	0.705	0.000
Academic achievement	73.71	7.007		

Table 7 shows that results of Pearson's Correlation used to find out correlation between Home Environment and Academic Achievement of students. The result indicated that there was a significant relationship between Home Environment (M=57.00, SD=8.360) and Academic Achievement (M=73.71, SD=7.007) of students. Table 4.19 further indicated there was a strong relationship between Home Environment and Academic Achievement as $r=0.462$.

Discussion

The aim of this study was to examine the relationship of home environment and academic achievement of elementary level students of Azad Jammu and Kashmir. The current study found that the importance of parental communication in facilitating students' academic success. Research consistently demonstrates that parental involvement, including effective communication between parents and children, positively impacts students' academic performance (Fan & Chen, 2001; Jeynes, 2005). Clear communication of academic expectations, parental interest in students' progress, and emphasis on studies are associated with improved academic achievement. The results also highlights the significance of the home learning environment, particularly in providing resources and support for students' academic endeavors. While the provision of learning materials and the establishment of study schedules are positively associated with academic achievement (Epstein, 2011), the absence of tutoring and limited television time suggests a potential area for further exploration. Although television viewing can have both positive and negative effects on students' academic performance (Gentile et al., 2017), setting appropriate limits may optimize its impact on learning.

Furthermore the results also found that the importance of emotional support within the family environment for students' academic success. Positive reinforcement, appreciation for students' qualities, and sharing success stories contribute to students' self-esteem and motivation, thereby enhancing academic achievement (Duchesne et al., 2007; Wentzel, 1998). However, the lack of polite correction for mistakes warrants attention, as constructive feedback is crucial for students' growth and development (Bloomquist et al., 2013). Moreover, the results highlight the positive relationships between different aspects of the home environment, such as parental communication, home learning environment, and emotional support, and students' academic achievement. These findings corroborate previous research indicating that a supportive home environment is a significant predictor of academic success (Desimone, 1999; Sui-Chu & Willms, 1996). Moreover, the observed correlations underscore the interconnectedness of various factors within the home environment and their collective influence on students' educational outcomes.

Conclusions

1. It is concluded that parental communication is basic aspect of home environment and is essential in academic achievement of students. Most of the students were agreed that the parent set clear targets, take interest for student's progress. Moreover, the parents emphasize on students studies.
2. It is concluded that the parental communication is important aspect in student's academic achievement. Majority of the respondents were disagreed that parents interact with teachers and discuss about the progress of studies with students.
3. It is concluded that home learning is the main aspect in home environment and play a dominant role in academic achievement of students. Most of the respondents were agreed that learning material is provided to students at home and tutor is not arrange for them. Moreover, students were allowed to watch television for specific time.
4. It is concluded that family members are very helpful in home learning by making schedule for students and in case of mistakes of students our rights are withdrawn.
5. It is concluded that respondents were in favor that emotional support is the main aspect in home environment and is correlated with academic achievement of students. Students agreed that family members appreciate their qualities and share their success stories with others. Moreover, family members do not improve them politely.
6. It is concluded that emotional support is helpful in student's academic achievement. Family members tell again them previous failures and parents attend their school programs.
7. It is concluded that there is strong positive relationship between the aspect of home environment parental communication and academic achievement of students.
8. It is concluded that there is positive relationship between the home environment aspect home learning environment and academic achievement of students.
9. It is concluded that there is relationship between that home environment aspect emotional support and academic achievement of students.

Recommendations

1. It is recommended that may improve parent-teacher communication, as over half of the students disagreed with the current level of interaction. Implement strategies such as regular meetings, newsletters, or online platforms to enhance parental involvement, encouragement a stronger connection between parents and teachers.
2. It is recommended that teacher parent may explore different methods of arranging home tutoring or improving communication to better meet students' first choice and needs for academic support.
3. It is recommended to encourage parent-child communication workshops or creativities to raise positive interaction. This may help association communication gaps and enhance the relationship between parents and students.
4. It is recommended to address the impact of family notices on students' perceptions of past failures. Implement supportive involvements to foster a positive environment and reinforce students' confidence in overcoming challenges, enhancing their comfort and academic performance.

References

- Ahmad, N., Shahzad, S., Zahid, M., Rauf, M., Azmat, M., & Shah, A. (2021). Assessment of Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement In The Subject Of Pakistan Study In Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. *Webology* (ISSN: 1735-188X), 18(5).
- Al-Matalqa, F. I. M. (2014). The influence of parental socioeconomic status on their involvement at home. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 4(5), 146-154.
- Al-Naggar, R. A., Osman, M. T., Ismail, Z., Bobryshev, Y. V., Ali, M. S., & Menendez-Gonzalez, M. (2015). Relation between type of personality and academic performance among Malaysian health sciences students. *International Archives of Medicine*, 8.
- Artino, A. R. (2012). Academic self-efficacy: from educational theory to instructional practice. *Perspectives on medical education*, 1, 76-85.
- Ben-Arieh, A., Casas, F., Frønes, I., & Korbin, J. E. (2014). Multifaceted concept of child well-being. *Handbook of child well-being*, 1, 1-27.
- Bicer, A., Capraro, M. M., & Capraro, R. (2013). The effects of parent's SES and education level on students' mathematics achievement: Examining the mediation effects of parental expectations and parental communication. *The Online Journal of New Horizons in Education*, 3(4), 89-97.
- Bick, J., Lipschutz, R., Lind, T., Zajac, L., & Dozier, M. (2019). Associations between early home environment and trajectories of disruptive behavior among preschoolers reared in CPS-referred families. *Developmental Child Welfare*, 1(4), 297-311.
- Bloomquist, M. L., August, G. J., Lee, S. S., Piehler, T. F., Jensen, M., & Hecht, D. B. (2013). Effects of a school-wide behavior management program implementation. *Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions*, 15(4), 202-213.
- Cetin, S. K., & Taskin, P. (2016). Parent involvement in education in terms of their socio-economic status. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 16(66), 105-122.
- Darling-Hammond, L., & Cook-Harvey, C. M. (2018). *Educating the Whole Child: Improving School Climate to Support Student Success*. Learning Policy Institute.
- Desimone, L. M. (1999). Linking parent involvement with student achievement: Do race and income matter? *Journal of Educational Research*, 93(1), 11-30.
- Donnelly, J. E., & Lambourne, K. (2011). Classroom-based physical activity, cognition, and academic achievement. *Preventive medicine*, 52, S36-S42.
- Duchesne, S., Ratelle, C. F., & Feng, B. (2007). Attachment security to mothers and fathers and the developmental trajectories of depressive symptoms in adolescence: Which parent for which trajectory? *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 36(7), 811-824.
- Duh, M., Belak, J., & Milfelner, B. (2010). Core values, culture and ethical climate as constitutional elements of ethical behaviour: Exploring differences between family and non-family enterprises. *Journal of business ethics*, 97, 473-489.
- Dzever, L. T. (2015). The Impact of Home Environment Factors on Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Garki Area District, Abuja-Nigeria. *Bulgarian Journal of Science & Education Policy*, 9(1).
- Efriza, R., Caska, C., & Makhdalena, M. (2020). Analysis of Factors Affecting Student Learning Achievement of Social Sciences Subjects in Muhammadiyah Middle School Rokan Hulu Regency. *Journal of Educational Sciences*, 4(3), 529-540.
- Epstein, J. L. (2011). *School, family, and community partnerships: Preparing educators and improving schools*. Westview Press.

- Fan, X., & Chen, M. (2001). Parental involvement and students' academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 13(1), 1-22.
- Fanti, K. A., & Henrich, C. C. (2010). Trajectories of pure and co-occurring internalizing and externalizing problems from age 2 to age 12: findings from the National Institute of Child Health and Human Development Study of Early Child Care. *Developmental psychology*, 46(5), 1159.
- Galvin, K. M., Braithwaite, D. O., & Bylund, C. L. (2015). *Family communication: Cohesion and change*. Routledge.
- Gentile, D. A., Nathanson, A. I., Rasmussen, E. E., Reimer, R. A., Walsh, D. A., & Eisenmann, J. C. (2017). Can watching TV hurt kids? Research explores how different forms of screen time affect children's health and development. *Child Development*, 88(2), 356-361.
- Harding, J. F., Morris, P. A., & Hughes, D. (2015). The relationship between maternal education and children's academic outcomes: A theoretical framework. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 77(1), 60-76.
- Hart, R. A. (2013). *Children's participation: The theory and practice of involving young citizens in community development and environmental care*. Routledge.
- Jeynes, W. H. (2005). A meta-analysis of the relation of parental involvement to urban elementary school student academic achievement. *Urban Education*, 40(3), 237-269.
- Kim, S. (2011). The effects of internet use on academic achievement and behavioral adjustment among South Korean adolescents: Mediating and moderating roles of parental factors. Syracuse University.
- Kim, S., & Esquivel, G. B. (2011). Adolescent spirituality and resilience: Theory, research, and educational practices. *Psychology in the Schools*, 48(7), 755-765.
- Kutsyuruba, B., Klinger, D. A., & Hussain, A. (2015). Relationships among school climate, school safety, and student achievement and well-being: a review of the literature. *Review of Education*, 3(2), 103-135.
- Mollborn, S., Rigles, B., & Pace, J. A. (2021). "Healthier than just healthy": Families transmitting health as cultural capital. *Social Problems*, 68(3), 574-590.
- Morin, P., Demers, K., Turcotte, S., & Mongeau, L. (2013). Association between perceived self-efficacy related to meal management and food coping strategies among working parents with preschool children. *Appetite*, 65, 43-50.
- Morin, P., Demers, K., Turcotte, S., & Mongeau, L. (2013). Association between perceived self-efficacy related to meal management and food coping strategies among working parents with preschool children. *Appetite*, 65, 43-50.
- Newman, J., Gozu, H., Guan, S., Lee, J. E., Li, X., & Sasaki, Y. (2015). Relationship between maternal parenting style and high school achievement and self-esteem in China, Turkey and USA. *Journal of Comparative Family Studies*, 46(2), 265-288.
- Nichols, T. M., Kotchick, B. A., McNamara Barry, C., & Haskins, D. G. (2010). Understanding the educational aspirations of African American adolescents: Child, family, and community factors. *Journal of Black Psychology*, 36(1), 25-48.
- Nouri, A. (2015). The relationship between Iranian EFL teachers' behavior and academic achievement of high school students. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 6(3), 574.
- O'Malley, M., Voight, A., Renshaw, T. L., & Eklund, K. (2015). School climate, family structure, and academic achievement: a study of moderation effects. *School Psychology Quarterly*, 30(1), 142.

- Runco, M. A., & Cayirdag, N. (2013). The development of children's creativity. In Handbook of research on the education of young children (pp. 116-128). Routledge.
- Ruthven, I., Buchanan, S., & Jardine, C. (2018). Relationships, environment, health and development: The information needs expressed online by young first-time mothers. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 69(8), 985-995.
- Sarsour, K., Sheridan, M., Jutte, D., Nuru-Jeter, A., Hinshaw, S., & Boyce, W. T. (2011). Family socioeconomic status and child executive functions: The roles of language, home environment, and single parenthood. *Journal of the International Neuropsychological Society*, 17(1), 120-132.
- Sharma, R. (2011). Effect of school and home environments on creativity of children. *MIER Journal of Educational Studies Trends and Practices*, 187-196.
- Sui-Chu, E. H., & Willms, J. D. (1996). Effects of parental involvement on eighth-grade achievement. *Sociology of Education*, 69(2), 126-141.
- Taylor, C. (2010). *A practical guide to caring for children and teenagers with attachment difficulties*. Jessica Kingsley Publishers.
- Wentzel, K. R. (1998). Social relationships and motivation in middle school: The role of parents, teachers, and peers. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 90(2), 202-209.
- Wood, R. G., Moore, Q., Clarkwest, A., & Killewald, A. (2014). The long-term effects of building strong families: A program for unmarried parents. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 76(2), 446-463.
- Yaffe, Y. (2023). Systematic review of the differences between mothers and fathers in parenting styles and practices. *Current psychology*, 42(19), 16011-16024.